

ENHANCING GOAT PRODUCTIVITY THROUGH EFFECTIVE REPRODUCTIVE MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Goat farming in India is a crucial occupation, particularly for small-scale farmers in rural and hilly regions, providing a source of income and employment. Proper reproductive management is essential for maximizing the benefits of goat farming, including improved productivity, health management, nutritional support, and breed conservation. By selecting high-yield breeds, ensuring proper healthcare, and providing balanced nutrition, farmers can improve both milk and meat production. Key components of reproductive management include understanding the reproductive cycle, selecting healthy breeding bucks, and utilizing techniques like natural mating and artificial insemination (AI). AI, in particular, offers significant advantages by enhancing genetic quality and increasing productivity. Additionally, careful pregnancy and parturition management ensure the birth of healthy kids. While there are challenges in goat farming, proper training, management practices, and support can ensure success, leading to better economic outcomes for farmers and rural communities, with a positive impact on India's agricultural landscape.

KEYWORDS: Goat Farming, Reproductive Management, Artificial Insemination, Breeding, Productivity, Rural Livelihoods

INTRODUCTION

India is an agricultural country, and along with agriculture, livestock farming is the main occupation of farmers, which they often rely on mutually. This occupation is a primary source of income for farmers in rural and hilly regions. Among all livestock, goat farming is the most accessible occupation because, from the perspective of small-scale farmers in hilly areas, it can be highly effective. If integrated and operated with entrepreneurial methods, this activity can enhance both income and employment opportunities to the farmers. A large portion of India's population depends directly or indirectly on this occupation. Due to the growing population and decreasing cultivable land, goat rearing will become the primary source of income for farmers in the future because their maintenance and feeding

can easily be managed by women and children on limited resources.

Goats are hardy animals that can survive in various environmental conditions. Goat farming is often referred to as "the poor man's cow" due to its affordability and utility for marginal farmers. According to the 2019 livestock census, the total goat population in India is 148.88 million, which constitutes 27.80% of the total livestock and contributes 3-4% of total milk production in the country.

Goat farming can be started on a small scale with minimal investment. Due to their high reproductive capacity and the ability to graze on bushes and tree leaves, as well as their adaptability to different environments, we can earn substantial profits from this business. These profits can come from selling their kids and milk, as well as using their manure as fertilizer on agricultural land.